

Effect of the Cross-Linking Density on the Thermoresponsive Behavior of Hollow PNIPAM Microgels

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S Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: We report on the fabrication of thermally responsive hollow pNIPAM particles through the oxidation of the metal core in an Au@pNIPAM system. The selective oxidation of the Au core is achieved by addition of AuCl_4^- to an aqueous dispersion of Au@pNIPAM particles in the presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB). We fabricate hollow pNIPAM particles with three cross-linking densities (*N,N'*-methylenebis(acrylamide), BA, at 5%, 10%, and 17.5%). The study of the effect of the amount of BA within the microgel network was performed by dynamic light scattering (DLS), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and atomic force microscopy (AFM), showing its key role in determining the final hollow structure and thermal response. While the thermal responsiveness is largely achieved at low cross-linking densities, the hollow structure only remains at larger cross-linking densities. This was further confirmed by cryo-TEM analysis of hollow pNIPAM particles below and above the volume phase transition temperature (VPTT). Thus, it clearly shows (i) the shrinking of particle size with the temperature at low cross-linking density and (ii) the dependence of particle size on the amount of cross-linker for the final hollow pNIPAM structure. Observed differences in the hollow pNIPAM structure are attributed to different elastic contributions (Π_{elas}), showing higher elasticity for microgels synthesized at lower amount of BA.

■ INTRODUCTION

A microgel is defined as a cross-linked polymeric particle of submicrometer size that remains dispersed in a certain fluid. They are normally obtained through polymerization of monomer molecules in the presence of a cross-linking agent.^{1,2} Microgels present high colloidal stability and certain degree of flexibility, but the most important advantage concerning microgels is their sensitivity to certain external stimuli, such as temperature,³ pH,⁴ solvent nature,⁵ ionic strength,⁶ or visible light.^{7,8} A change in an external stimulus causes the microgel to change in volume between two states, referred to as swollen and collapsed state. In 1986, Pelton and Chibante reported, for the first time, the synthesis of a temperature-sensitive aqueous microgel based on poly(*N*-isopropylacrylamide) (pNIPAM).² This polymer has a volume phase transition temperature (VPTT) at 32 °C in water. Below this temperature, the microgel has high water content, low refractive index difference with water, and few electrically charged groups on the surface. In contrast, above the VPTT, the microgel contains lower amount of water molecules, high

density of charged groups, and a greater refractive index difference with water.

During the past decades, pNIPAM has probably become one of the most studied thermoresponsive polymer, not only for the remarkable properties and applications involving colloidal particles^{8,9} but also because pNIPAM collapses at a temperature near the human body. In consequence, these stimulus-responsive particles have gained considerable attention by exploiting the possibility to deliver drugs in a specific position induced by temperature, which has an enormous interest in several biomedical fields, such as biosensor technology,^{10,11} biological coatings,^{12–14} and controlled drug delivery.^{15–17} However, for this last purpose, better than pure microgels, hollow particles may hold even more significant interest due to their improved capacity in the encapsulation of molecules as polysaccharides, enzymes, nucleic acids, or cells,^{18–20} which can

be used as stable temperature-triggered microcontainers.²¹ During past years several methods and protocols have been reported for the fabrication of hollow pNIPAM microspheres: (i) encapsulation of colloidal particles, such as gold, silica, or polycaprolactone, with a pNIPAM shell and a subsequent treatment with NaOH, KCN, HF, or the enzyme lipase (for instance, a lipolase solution 8 vol % from Novozymes), respectively, to remove the core;^{22–28} (ii) free radical polymerization of pNIPAM in the presence of a comonomer, which is subsequently degraded by acid or basic treatment;^{29,30} (iii) synthesis of a nuclei formed by non-cross-linked pNIPAM oligomers which is used as template for a subsequent pNIPAM cross-linked coating;^{31,32} and (iv) layer-by-layer assembly of oppositely charged thermoresponsive polyelectrolytes on colloidal particles as silica or gold which are then removed to obtain a thermoresponsive hollow structure.^{33,34}

Recently, cryo-TEM has been used as a technique to study complex fluids and biological systems³⁵ as well as to characterize colloidal particles composed by a nuclei with different attached structure, such as polymer brushes, polyelectrolytes chains, or cross-linked networks.^{36,37} This technique is normally employed to visualize the behavior of the particles in the aqueous phase by shock-freezing of a suspension of particles. Specifically, the volume transition of pNIPAM has been previously observed by cryo-TEM analysis in polystyrene particles grafted with pNIPAM,^{38,39} but no studies of core@shell metal@pNIPAM or hollow thermoresponsive microgels by this technique have been reported to date.

In this work we present a new method for the fabrication of hollow pNIPAM particles from core@shell Au@pNIPAM particles with different cross-linking densities and the first reported analysis of hollow pNIPAM particles by cryo-TEM investigations. The procedure is based on the encapsulation of spherical gold nanoparticles by a pNIPAM shell, followed by the selective oxidation of the gold core, while the thermoresponsive shell remains unaltered. The general process is represented in Scheme 1. The gold core oxidation was

Scheme 1. Schematic Representation for the Gradual Oxidation of the Gold Core and the Fabrication of Hollow pNIPAM Microgels Using Au@pNIPAM Particles as Templates in Aqueous Au³⁺/CTAB Mixtures^a

^aThe numbers correspond to the average gold nanoparticle size as determined by TEM.

performed for three different Au@pNIPAM systems with the same gold core size but with different cross-linker percentages (5, 10, and 17.5%, respectively). UV–vis spectroscopy, DLS, TEM, and AFM were used to monitor the oxidation process and to characterize the hollow pNIPAM morphology. Cryo-TEM investigations performed on hollow pNIPAM systems (5 and 10% BA) below and above the LCST confirmed that the hollow structure was only observed above 5% content of BA

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), 3-butenic acid (97%), and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM, 97%) were supplied

by Aldrich. Tetrachloroauric acid (HAuCl₄·3H₂O) and trisodium citrate dihydrate were supplied by Sigma. *N,N'*-Methylenebis-(acrylamide) (BA) was supplied by Fluka. 2,2'-Azobis(2-methylpropanamidene) dihydrochloride (AAPH) was supplied by Across Organics. All reactants were used without further purification. Water was purified using a Milli-Q system (Millipore).

Synthesis of Au@pNIPAM. To carry out the encapsulation of gold nanoparticles with pNIPAM, first ~64 nm gold nanoparticles were prepared through a modification of the seeded growth method based on the reduction of HAuCl₄ with 3-butenic acid on CTAB-stabilized Au nanoparticles seeds in the presence of CTAB.⁴⁰ Briefly, 35 mL of ca. 15 nm citrate-stabilized Au nanoparticles (prepared by citrate reduction) was added to 15 mL of 0.03 M CTAB aqueous solution. Then a growth solution was prepared by adding 800 μL of butenoic acid to 50 mL of an aqueous solution containing 1 mM HAuCl₄ and 15 mM CTAB. Subsequently, 4.5 mL of the seed solution was added under gentle magnetic stirring to the growth solution at 70 °C. After 10 min, excess butenoic acid and CTAB were removed by centrifugation at 4500 rpm for 30 min. After redispersing the pellet in 50 mL of 4 mM CTAB, the dispersion was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 40 min, and the final precipitate was redispersed in 10 mL of water. For the pNIPAM encapsulation, this amount of Au colloidal dispersion was heated to 70 °C under N₂ flow. Then, three different systems were prepared, containing NIPAM 0.1698 g (1.503 mmol, 100%) in every case but with different amount of *N,N'*-methylenebis(acrylamide); 0.0117 g (5 mol %), 0.0234 g (10 mol %), and 0.0409 g (17.5 mol %), respectively, under magnetic stirring. After 15 min, the nitrogen flow was removed and the polymerization was initiated with the addition of AAPH (100 μL 0.1 M) in each case. After 7–10 min the reddish solution became turbid, and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 3 h at 70 °C. The mixture was allowed to cool down at room temperature under stirring. Finally, it was diluted with water (50 mL), centrifuged (30 min at 4500 rpm), and redispersed in water (5-fold). It is important to note that the used amounts of cross-linker are only nominal values; the real cross-linking density within the microgel is unknown. Besides we should consider the inhomogeneous cross-linking density distribution inside the microgel, which gives rise to a more cross-linked interior, being more pronounced as the cross-linker content increases.^{41,42}

Gold Core Oxidation. Gold metal oxidation was performed through the same procedure previously developed by Rodríguez-Fernández et al.⁴³ Briefly, 5 mL of the Au@pNIPAM particles at [Au] = 0.5 mM was immersed in 5 mL of a solution containing CTAB (100 mM) and HAuCl₄ (0.125 mM) at 28 °C under mild magnetic stirring. The final solution was allowed to react for 80 min, and then it was centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 1 h in order to remove the CTAB excess and possible byproducts generated during the oxidation process. The supernatant was removed, and the precipitate was redispersed in 10 mL of water. Controlling the Au@pNIPAM to gold salt ratio allows to control the extent of the core oxidation. The general procedure is represented in Scheme 1.

Characterization. UV–vis–NIR absorption spectra were recorded using an Agilent 8453 UV–vis diode array spectrophotometer in a 1 cm quartz cell. Transmission electron microscopy was carried out by using a JEOL JEM 1010 microscope operating at an acceleration voltage of 100 kV. Samples were prepared by drying a drop of 10 μL of colloidal suspension on a carbon-coated copper grid. Atomic force microscopy analysis was carried out in tapping mode with a VEECO RTESP tip of $k = 20\text{--}80 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ (exact spring constant not calculated) using a Nanoscope V controller on a multimode microscope. Dynamic light scattering measurements were performed on a Zetasizer Nano S (Malvern Instruments, Malvern UK) using a detection angle of 173°. The Nano S used a 4 mW He–Ne laser operating at a wavelength of 633 nm. The intensity-averaged particle diameter and the polydispersity index values were calculated from cumulant-type analysis.

Cryo-TEM images were taken on a Libra 120 TEM (Zeiss, Germany) at an acceleration voltage of 120 kV, operated in low-dose mode and equipped with a 2k CCD camera (Troendle, Germany). To increase contrast, the images were taken with a zero-loss energy filter. To visualize the inside of the particles, the images were background

Figure 1. Representative TEM images of the Au@pNIPAM particles before (A) and after (B) partial gold core oxidation. (C) Time evolution of the UV-vis-NIR absorption spectrum during oxidation process. The spectra were recorded every 4 min. The arrow indicates the spectrum of sample shown in (B). (D) Gold core particle size distribution histograms before (white columns) and after 16 min (gray columns) of oxidation reaction. The inset shows the corresponding average size together with the standard deviation.

corrected using an internal pixel comparison algorithm of the software iTEM (Olympus, Japan). Cryo-TEM tomography was executed at FEI Nanoport, Eindhoven, on a Technai G2 (FEI), with 200 kV acceleration voltage and a FEI Eagle camera, using the proprietary software. 3D-reconstruction of the tomography was carried out using IMOD software. For all cryo-TEM specimens, the suspensions of particles were vitrified using an EM-GP1 plunger (Leica, Germany), equipped with an environmental chamber set to 100% air humidity and 25 °C for swollen and 50 °C for collapsed specimens, respectively. For each specimen, a droplet (3.5 μL) of the suspension was applied to a QF R2.2 grid (Quantifoil, Germany). Prior to use, the grids were activated for 30 s in oxygen plasma using a Femto plasma cleaner (DienerElectronic, Germany). After blotting the droplet with filter paper, the grid was shot into liquid ethane at a temperature of 88 K (−185 °C) for vitrification of a thin liquid film. After preparation, the grids were kept in liquid nitrogen until they were inserted into a CT3500 cryo-TEM holder (Gatan) and kept at 98 K (−175 °C) during analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Au@pNIPAM nanocomposites constituted by ~ 64 nm Au core and pNIPAM shell (see Figure 1A) are synthesized as starting materials to obtain hollow pNIPAM microgels. The synthesis of the hollow microgels requires the selective oxidation of the gold core. Such selective gold oxidation can be achieved through the addition of HAuCl_4 to an aqueous dispersion of Au@pNIPAM in CTAB. Upon mixing, the gold salt precursor will strongly bind to CTA monomers, through an ion-pair formation (AuCl_4^- -CTA), and will be readily solubilized in the CTAB micelles.⁴³ The high porosity of the microgel network is exploited in order to allow the diffusion of Au^{3+} -CTAB complexes through the pNIPAM shell, reaching the gold nanoparticle surface. It has been previously reported that the strong binding of CTA monomers to AuCl_2^- and AuCl_4^- will lead to a shift in the equilibrium constant of the conproportionation reaction (see eq 1).⁴³

The sole presence of CTAB will affect the value of the redox potentials and therefore the equilibrium constant, being reaction 1 basically stoichiometric (that is, with a very high equilibrium constant) and leading to the gold core oxidation. This CTAB-induced oxidation process can be analyzed through UV-vis-NIR absorption spectroscopy following the time evolution of the localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) from Au@pNIPAM at 540 nm and the absorption band from the Au^{3+} -CTAB complex at 400 nm. As it can be observed in Figure 1C, a decrease in the LSPR intensity is observed which suggests a decrease in the metal size during oxidation. Interestingly, it is important to note that there was no significant displacement of the localized surface plasmon (LSPR) band position during the reaction process. In principle, a decrease in the gold core size should produce a blue-shift in the LSPR band, but we have to take into account the contribution to the extinction spectrum of the scattering effect and the fact the oxidation process could be not homogeneous, leading to an invariance of the LSPR during the oxidation. Additionally, it clearly indicates that the Au^{3+} -CTAB complex is able to diffuse through the microgel network, reaching the gold nanoparticle surface and finally producing the gold core oxidation. The reaction stops after the total consumption/reduction of Au^{3+} ions supplied by the HAuCl_4 solution according to eq 1. The band located at 400 nm after the total gold oxidation corresponds to the excess Au^{3+} -CTAB complex that remains in solution. The total gold core oxidation can be achieved, in the presence of CTAB, at Au(III):Au(0) ratios above 0.5:1.0 (see Experimental Section for details). The absence of plasmon band at the end of reaction suggests the total removal of the gold core. To confirm the Au core oxidation, TEM analysis was carried out. Figure 1 shows representative TEM images of Au@pNIPAM particles before (Figure 1A) and after 16 min (Figure 1B) and 120 min (Figure

Figure 2. Representative TEM images of hollow pNIPAM particles with different BA percentages: (A) 5%, (B) 10%, and (C) 17.5%. The insets show representative particles at higher magnification; scale bars represent 200 nm. (D) Variation with the temperature of the hydrodynamic diameter of Au@pNIPAM particles with 5% (circle symbols), 10% (square symbols), and 17.5% (triangles) BA cross-linking before and after (open and closed symbols, respectively) the oxidation process. The red, blue, and black lines are a guide to the eye.

2A) of the oxidation process. While a decrease in the average metal core dimension can be easily observed, until total particle oxidation, the process does not seem to affect the particles morphology. The extinction spectrum of sample after 16 min is denoted with an arrow in Figure 1C. The latter confirms the homogeneous diffusion of the Au^{3+} -CTAB complex through the microgel shell. Figure 1D shows size distribution histograms of Au gold cores before (red columns) and after (black columns) 16 min core oxidation obtained by TEM analysis. Thus, in 16 min of oxidation process gold core decreases from 63.9 ± 5.9 to 38.8 ± 4.3 nm. In certain cases, it is possible to observe the presence of free microgels (see Figure 1B), which correspond to free pNIPAM microgels from the pNIPAM encapsulation of gold nanoparticles that were not totally removed during the Au@pNIPAM purification step (see Experimental Section for details). The Au core oxidation was also studied for Au@pNIPAM microgels fabricated with different BA amounts (5% and 17.5%), and similar results were obtained (data not shown).

The total gold core oxidation gives rise to hollow pNIPAM microgels (Figure 2). Besides, these structures can be obtained from Au@pNIPAM samples containing 5, 10, and 17.5% BA, as revealed by the absence of any residual gold nanoparticles inside the pNIPAM microgels. Therefore, the complete oxidation of the core occurs independently of the BA added. In addition, TEM images also reveal the presence of a hole within the pNIPAM structure in at least 90% of the microgels for the samples with 10% and 17.5% BA content (Figures 2B and 2C, respectively). Surprisingly such a hole is not observed by TEM in any of the microgels with a 5% BA content after the core oxidation (see Figure 2A). The hollow microgels fabricated with the highest cross-linker (BA) content (17.5%) appear to be an aggregation of nodules with holes (see Figure 2C); this effect can be attributed to the inhomogeneous polymerization at high BA contents and to the drying process during TEM preparation. The deviation from sphericity in Figures 2A and 2C compared to Figure 2B was not observed in

the DLS measurements (showing low polydispersity indexes in all cases) which are perfectly suited to study microgels. We believe that it is caused by the drying process during the TEM grid preparation.

Further characterization of the hollow samples was performed by means of photon correlation spectroscopy. Figure 2D displays the variation of the hydrodynamic diameter when the temperature is raised from 15 to 55 °C for Au@pNIPAM particles with 5 and 10% BA before and after total gold core elimination. Thus, a well-defined volume phase transition temperature at about 32 °C can be observed for both Au@pNIPAM and hollow-pNIPAM and for 5 and 10% BA (see discussion below). This indicates that the VPTT remains unchanged despite of the hollow core. Unfortunately, the difference in size shown by Au@pNIPAM microgels with different BA contents in the collapsed state does not allow a straightforward comparison between them. In any case, the cross-linking density effect in the collapsed state for the different BA contents can be easily visualized by plotting the shrinking ratio (the inverse of the swelling ratio) versus temperature for the different nanocomposites (see Figure S1 in the Supporting Information). The swelling ratio is defined as the ratio between the volume of the microgel in the swollen state (at 20 °C) and the volume of the microgels at each temperature ($\beta = V_{\text{swollen}}(20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})/V(T)$). For instance, at collapse state the removal of the Au core leads to a volume decrease by a factor of 2 for pNIPAM composites with 5% BA content while the volume remains almost constant for microgels with 10% and 17.5% BA (see Figure S1, Supporting Information). These results suggest that at 10% and 17.5% BA contents the microgel network collapses without affecting the structure of the hole. A possible explanation for this cross-linker-dependence behavior can be extracted from Flory's theory.⁴⁴ It is well-known that the swelling capacity in a neutral microgel is controlled by the balance between mixture and elastic osmotic pressure (Π_{mix} and Π_{elas} , respectively). A polymer with a low cross-linking density experiences an abrupt

Figure 3. AFM topography images of hollow pNIPAM particles with different cross-linking densities. (A) Phase image and (B) height image and profile of a particle with 5% BA. (C) 2D and 3D (inset) amplitude images and (D) height image and profile of a particle with 10% BA. (E) 2D and 3D (inset) amplitude images and (F) height image and profile of a particle with 17.5% BA.

phase transition due to a lower elasticity component.⁴⁴ With increasing the cross-linking density, the competition between solvency and elasticity is more intense, increasing the rigidity of the system. In the present case, the elastic component for hollow pNIPAM microgel containing 5% of BA in the hollow pNIPAM network is not able to avoid a total collapse during the drying process; therefore, no residual hole is observed after drying on the TEM grid. However, at higher cross-linker percentages (10% and 17.5% BA) the elastic component of the hollow pNIPAM system is strong enough to avoid total

microgel shrinking during collapse, showing thus the presence of a small hole.

Additional evidence of the previous behavior was obtained from AFM analysis. Figure 3 shows representative AFM images of dry hollow microgel samples prepared with different BA content and deposited on silicon wafer substrates, providing confirmation of the core-shell structure. Figures 3B, 3D, and 3F show height images of the pNIPAM microgel containing 5%, 10%, and 17.5% BA, respectively. The height profiles show a hemispherical shape at the lowest cross-linker percentage (5% BA) while for higher BA content (10% and 17.5%) a sudden

Figure 4. Representative cryo-TEM images at different magnifications showing hollow microgels containing 5% and 10% BA below and above the LCST: (A) 5% BA and 25 °C, (B) 5% BA and 50 °C, (C) 10% BA and 25 °C, and (D) 10% BA and 50 °C.

Figure 5. Slides through the reconstructed volume of a cryo-TEM tomography of a hollow microgel obtained from Au@pNIPAM (see text for details). Panels A, B, and C represent the upper, middle, and lower part of the reconstructed volume, respectively.

collapse can be easily distinguished close to the center of the microgel. Taking into account the effect of the cross-linking density in the height profiles of the parent Au@pNIPAM composites (see Figure 2 in ref 45), this behavior could be attributed to the absence or the presence of a hollow core as the pNIPAM shell dehydrates. While for the lowest cross-linking content (5%) upon drying the pNIPAM shell shrinks producing the hollow core collapse and disappear, for the higher cross-linking percentages (10% and 17.5%) the higher rigidity of the shell makes the hollow core remains upon drying. All this results are in good agreement with the results observed by TEM analysis. Additionally, we have to consider that starting Au@pNIPAM microgels with the different BA contents do not

present the same size in the collapse state (see Figure 2D) which makes the comparison between the different height profiles difficult.

All the previous data support that the thermoresponsive capabilities of the hollow pNIPAM are affected by the amount of BA within the microgel network, and they have an important influence in the final morphology of the hollow structure. As was mentioned in the Introduction, cryo-TEM investigations have emerged as a powerful technique to characterize essentially *in situ* colloidal systems (in frozen state) which are normally composed by a colloidal core with grafted polymer brushes, polyelectrolyte chains, or block copolymer.^{36,46} This technique is used to visualize the structure in aqueous medium

by shock-freezing a solution or suspension of the system keeping the original structure. To the best of our knowledge there are no detailed studies of hollow thermoresponsive microgels published to date. Figure 4 shows representative cryo-TEM images for hollow pNIPAM systems vitrified at 25 and 50 °C containing 5% and 10% BA. While no hole is observed for the hollow pNIPAM with 5% BA and particles resemble pure pNIPAM microgels (Figure 4A,B), hollow pNIPAM particles with 10% BA exhibit a hollow structure (Figure 4C,D). The morphology of the particles with 10% BA does not change above the VPTT, and the average diameter measured by cryo-TEM decreases from 355 to 310 nm. This very low change of diameter compared to DLS (see Figure 2D) can be explained by two effects: Primarily, the contrast on the cryo-TEM images is solely caused by the different electron densities of the microgel and the surrounding water; thus, the hydrodynamic shell around the particle is not affecting TEM imaging and DLS in the same fashion. Additionally, the background correction algorithm, used to improve the visibility of the microgel, blurs the area around objects with higher contrast (visible by the white rim around the particles), leading to an apparent enlargement of the collapsed particles. Furthermore, this blurring impedes reliable measurements of the diameter of the microgel with 5% BA, as no clear spherical or hollow structure is visible on the images.

In an attempt to shed some light on the structure of the hollow pNIPAM, a full structural characterization is required, and since conventional cryo-TEM techniques only provide 2D projections and AFM has limited resolution, the morphology of the hollow pNIPAM was elucidated by electron tomography. Figure 5 shows three slices taken from the 3D reconstruction of a tomographic series (see Supporting Information video): the first one from the upper part, the second from the middle, and the third from the bottom of the reconstructed volume. The three images show a hollow structure, and the sizes of the particles and holes are comparable to the previously taken cryo-TEM images, verifying the 2D recordings acquired before and proving that the particles possess a hollow structure.

■ CONCLUSION

We have reported the synthesis of hollow pNIPAM microgels via the selective oxidation of the gold core of Au@pNIPAM composites. The influence of three different cross-linker densities (5, 10, and 17.5% BA) on the temperature-dependent morphology of the hollow pNIPAM shell was studied by means of DLS, TEM, and AFM. The results showed that in the collapse state (above the VPTT) the hollow structure depends remarkably on the cross-linking density within the microgel. For cross-linker densities above 5% the pNIPAM capsules remained hollow even at temperatures higher than the VPTT. We have also reported for the first time a cryo-TEM investigation of hollow pNIPAM particles. These experiments confirmed that the absence/presence of the hollow structure is related with the amount of cross-linker. This dependence can be exploited for the fabrication of thermoresponsive microcontainers with controllable loading capabilities, with potential drug delivery applications in the encapsulation of proteins, polymers, or drugs and for the incorporation of functional molecules or nanoparticles to provide a responsive system with thermoresponsive release.

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Notes

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